

LISTENING FOR ALZHEIMER'S CLUES: CAN AUTOMATED SPEECH ANALYSIS CAPTURE DISTINCT PATTERNS ACROSS SEXES?

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Aims: Automated speech analysis (ASA) was used to differentiate between stages of cognitive impairment. Additionally, a sex-based analysis of the digital speech protocol was explored.

Methods: Since 2022, patients evaluated at the Memory Clinic of Ace Alzheimer Center Barcelona completed a digital speech protocol (~3 min) that included an image description, a semantic verbal fluency (SVF) test, and a description of a personal experience. Acoustic (n=1203) and linguistic (n=228) features were extracted to discriminate among diagnosis groups: Subjective Cognitive Decline (SCD), Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI), and Alzheimer's disease (AD) dementia. The SHAP framework identified the most significant features contributing to the Machine Learning (ML) model's performance. Finally, a sex-based analysis explored whether the models were prone to sex-based errors and examined the most significant feature differences between men and women.

Results: The study included 2140 participants (mean age 75.8, 65.3% female): 249 with SCD, 1209 with MCI, and 682 with AD dementia. Discrimination analysis between diagnostic group pairs showed AUCs of 0.98 for SCD vs ADD, 0.82 for SCD vs MCI, and 0.76 for MCI vs ADD. The most significant features on the ML model were the number of unique animals and the word frequencies on the SVF test. The models were not prone to sex-based errors ($p>0.05$), and the top-5 most significant features were common across sexes, except acoustic shimmer, which was a significant feature for women but not for men in distinguishing SCD vs MCI.

Conclusion: This study demonstrates the effectiveness of ASA, a low cost, non-invasive and easy applicable tool, in distinguishing between different stages of cognitive impairment. For the first time, it is shown that digital speech biomarkers are robust across sexes.